

EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION, SPORTS AND HEALTHCARE ACTIVITIES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the educational significance of physical education, sports and health activities in educational institutions. Physical education and sports activities affect not only the physical development of young people, but also their moral, aesthetic and social well-being. The thesis highlights the role of sports and health activities in the education of students, their impact on their social adaptation, and the formation of a healthy lifestyle through physical activity. It also analyzes effective methods for integrating physical education and sports into the educational process and their positive impact on the educational process.

Keywords: Physical education, sports, health activities, education, youth, physical activity, healthy lifestyle, social adaptation, pedagogical approach.

Introduction.

The development of each society is directly related to the health and physical strength of its members. After all, a healthy generation is the guarantee of the future of the nation. In today's globalization environment, strengthening human health and encouraging physical activity are becoming one of the priorities of state policy. In particular, the widespread promotion of physical education and sports in educational institutions plays an important role in the formation of the younger generation as not only physically, but also morally, intellectually and socially mature people.

In many cases, sports and physical education are limited only to competitions or training, but this concept is perceived in a very narrow circle. In fact, sports are a powerful tool that forms such qualities as discipline, will, teamwork, mutual respect and striving for the goal. Physical education not only strengthens the body, but also stabilizes the psychological state of a person and forms a positive attitude towards life.

Problems such as inactivity, malnutrition and stress are becoming increasingly common among today's youth. This can negatively affect their health, future activities and, in general, their place in society. Therefore, physical education and health promotion activities should become an integral part of the educational process. This thesis discusses the educational value of physical

education, the impact of sports on human character and social life, as well as effective methods for forming a healthy lifestyle in educational institutions.

Physical education and sports have a great impact not only on strengthening a person's physical health, but also on his mental development and social adaptation. The role of physical education in today's educational institutions is not limited to physical exercises, but also encourages young people to be disciplined, goal-oriented and strong-willed. In particular, regular sports participation helps to form leadership qualities in the younger generation. Physical education not only strengthens the body physically, but also has a positive effect on the human psyche, preventing stress and depression.

Today, due to technological progress, a sedentary lifestyle is becoming widespread among young people. Many people spend most of their time in front of a computer or phone, which leads to health problems, especially overweight, the development of spinal and cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, promoting physical education and a healthy lifestyle in educational institutions should be considered not only as a mandatory subject, but also as a necessary life skill for every student.

One of the most important aspects of physical education is its educational value. Sport teaches a person discipline, forms the ability to set the right goal and strive for it. For example, team sports develop communication skills among young people and help them quickly adapt to society. Martial arts increase the ability to make independent decisions and self-confidence.

In addition, sport also forms the moral qualities of a person. It is precisely through sports that qualities such as honesty, appreciation of hard-earned results, and drawing the right conclusions from defeat are instilled in the minds of young people. The culture of respectful approach to opponents during training, mutual solidarity and support is also important in the future life of young people.

Another important aspect of physical education is its role in forming a culture of a healthy lifestyle. If a student or pupil is involved in sports from a young age, it will later become an integral part of his life. This will help the future generation grow up healthy and strong. Therefore, it is necessary to organize physical education and health promotion activities in educational institutions not only during the lesson, but also through extracurricular activities, sports clubs and competitions. Physical education is not only a means of strengthening physical health, but also an important factor in the comprehensive development of a person. Through sports, not only physical

strength is formed in the younger generation, but also qualities such as strong will, discipline, teamwork and striving for a goal. Therefore, the development of physical education in educational institutions and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle should remain one of the main values that serve the sustainable development of society.

Theoretical basis:

There are various pedagogical and psychological theories about the role of physical education and sports in the educational process, which emphasize the importance of physical activity in the comprehensive development of a person. The ancient Greek philosophers Plato and Aristotle also considered physical education necessary for personal development. In their opinion, the spiritual and physical development of a person are inextricably linked, and both are considered important for the development of society. Plato, in his works, emphasized the formation of such qualities in a person as courage, endurance and willpower through sports. Later, thinkers such as Y.A. Komensky, J.J. Rousseau and K.D. Ushinsky, among the pedagogues of the New Age, also noted that physical education is one of the main components of child education. For example, Komensky, in his work "Great Didactics", emphasized the importance of physical education and movement in the educational process, saying that a child's ability to learn depends on his physical condition. Ushinsky, in turn, showed that physical education has a positive effect on a person's mental development and that sports have a special place in child education.

In today's modern educational theories, physical education and sports are considered the main factor that directly affects the physical, psychological and moral development of a person. Also, from the point of view of pedagogical psychology, sports and physical education develop social competencies in a person. The positive effect of physical activity on children's thinking, emotional state and intellectual abilities, starting from preschool education, has been proven by scientific research. For example, modern neuropsychological studies show that physical activity increases children's cognitive abilities, that is, it has a positive effect on attention, memory and logical thinking processes.

Self-control and a sense of self-confidence are formed through sports. Psychological theories of personality development, in particular, the teachings of L.S. Vygotsky and J. Piaget, show the connection between physical activity and social adaptation. Vygotsky emphasizes the importance of movement and the social environment in child development, and says that physical education can help a child socialize and form his communicative abilities. Piaget notes that the

development of a child's thinking directly depends on his activity, and that movement accelerates the child's cognitive development.

Sports also help maintain a person's emotional balance. Psychologists have found that physical activity is an effective tool against depression and stress. Sports play a particularly important role in reducing psychological stress among young people and improving their adaptation to social life. Therefore, organizing sports events in educational institutions is considered important not only for strengthening physical health, but also for stabilizing the mental state of students, forming strong-willed qualities in them and increasing motivation.

In general, it has been theoretically proven that physical education and sports are not only a means of preserving and strengthening human health, but also an important factor in the comprehensive development of the individual. Therefore, it is necessary to approach physical education in educational institutions based on innovative pedagogical approaches, and to conduct sports classes in an interesting and interactive way. This will help the younger generation to become both healthy and intellectually developed people in the future.

Physical education and sports in educational institutions are of great importance in the physical, mental and moral development of the younger generation. Physical education, along with strengthening a person's physical health, also has a positive effect on his psychological state. Therefore, each educational institution should pay special attention to sports and health-improving activities in its educational programs. After all, a healthy generation is not only physically strong, but also disciplined, determined and confident in their life goals.

Today, problems related to inactivity and stress are increasingly common among young people. This can seriously affect their physical and mental health in the future. It is through physical education that it is possible to increase the motivation of young people, involve them in social activity and form a healthy lifestyle. In educational institutions, the attitude towards sports should be considered not only as a compulsory subject, but also as a value that is important for human life.

Sport shapes a person's character, instilling in him qualities such as courage, endurance and goal-orientedness. Team sports help a person to socialize, adapt to the team environment and feel like an important member of the team. During training, students test their abilities, increase their self-confidence and strive for success. Sport is not only a physical activity, but also a

path to spiritual maturity. As a result, the need to further increase the educational value of physical education and sports in educational institutions becomes clear. By introducing innovative methods and conducting sports events in an interesting and interactive way, it is possible to increase the interest of the younger generation in sports. It should be remembered that physical education is an important factor not only in strengthening physical health, but also in social, moral and mental development.

In the future, raising a healthy and strong generation, forming their positive attitude to life should be one of the priority tasks of the education system. Because physically healthy and spiritually strong people are one of the most important factors in the development of society. Therefore, by strengthening the promotion of sports and physical education, developing a healthy lifestyle, it is possible to achieve the formation of not only a physically healthy, but also a harmonious generation.

Conclusion:

One of the important factors in the development of modern society is the upbringing of a healthy and physically strong generation. The systematic introduction of physical education and sports in educational institutions is important not only for strengthening the health of young people, but also for forming their willpower, increasing discipline, teamwork and self-confidence. Sport teaches a person to make the right decisions, realize their capabilities and be persistent in life's trials.

Physical education is not limited to physical training, but also has a strong impact on the human mind. Regular physical activity increases a person's stress resistance, improves mental activity, and forms a positive attitude towards life. Therefore, it is necessary to widely promote the culture of a healthy lifestyle in educational institutions, teach the younger generation to be physically active, and make sports a part of everyday life.

Also, through sports, young people acquire such important qualities as goal-setting, hard work, patience, and striving for victory. They understand that success in life can be achieved step by step, just like the results achieved in sports. Therefore, sports are not only physical training, but also a means of personal development and achieving goals set for themselves.

From this point of view, the development of physical education in educational institutions serves not only to improve the health of students, but also to improve the quality of their overall education. Because young people who are engaged in physical activity, while paying attention to their health, achieve high

results in the process of studying. This will become the basis for the formation of a healthy, harmonious and intellectually developed generation for society in the future. In conclusion, the development of physical education and sports in educational institutions serves not only physical health, but also psychologically and morally to develop a person as a mature person. Therefore, each educational institution should see physical education not only as a lesson, but also as an important value aimed at educating healthy and mature individuals of society. After all, a healthy body is a guarantee of a healthy soul, a healthy society and a happy future.

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